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Mechanical Technology Practical Skills Required For Employability Of Undergraduates As A Means Of Improving National Pride In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The employability of mechanical technology graduates has become a critical concern in developing economies, particularly Nigeria, where unemployment among engineering graduates continues to rise despite increasing industrial demands. Studies indicate that over 70% of Nigerian engineering graduates lack industry-standard practical skills, limiting their employability and contribution to national development. This paper investigates the mechanical technology practical skills required for undergraduate employability as a pathway to improving national pride. Using a descriptive research approach and drawing from recent empirical studies, industry reports, and employer perspectives, the study identifies major skill gaps, curriculum inadequacies, infrastructural deficiencies, and weak industry–institution collaboration. Findings reveal that competencies such as machining operations, equipment maintenance, CAD/CAM applications, problem-solving, teamwork, and workplace ethics are essential for employability. The paper concludes that strengthening practical skill acquisition through once a week hands-on work-integrated learning, mentoring, curriculum reform, and improved training facilities and materials, scheduling will enhance graduate employability, boost industrial productivity, and foster national pride. Recommendations are offered for policymakers, institutions, and industry stakeholders.

Keywords: Mechanical Technology, Practical Skills, Employability, Undergraduates, National Pride

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, particularly from COVID-19 till date, the global labor market has increasingly emphasized that employability skills are much more relevant over mere academic qualifications. Despite steady improvements in the global economy, employment challenges still remain, and increasingly severe in many parts of the world (Ukpong, 2025). According to IMF projections, global economic growth was expected to reach 5.5% in 2021 before slowing to 4.2% in 2022 (International Monetary Fund, 2025). This economic recovery however, has not translated into sufficient job creation, particularly in developing and least developed countries like Nigeria, among others (Ukpong, 2025).

As a core field within technical and vocational education, Mechanical technology plays a very vital role in industrial growth, technological advancement, and national development in developing nations, especially Nigeria (Daniels, 2023). Mechanical technology brings together the fields of metalwork and automobile technology. Broadly, it can be organized into two main areas: metal production and automobile systems. Each of these areas includes a range of specialized occupations that require specific technical training. Within metalwork technology, common roles include metal casting and foundry work, sheet metal

fabrication, welding, machining, and structural steel construction, among others (Olowe, 2024). Automobile mechanics have access to a wide variety of employment opportunities. These include tasks such as engine cleaning and tuning, lubrication services, mechanical repairs, brake system maintenance, front-end servicing, auto-electrical work, air-conditioning repairs, bodywork restoration, and shop or service station management. Other areas under mechanical technological practice includes spray painting, interior upholstery, chassis repairs, vulcanization, radiator servicing, crankshaft machining, engine rebuilding, wheel alignment, tire balancing, driving services, and technical instruction in automotive trades (Elom et al., 2021).

In Nigeria and other developing economies in Africa, mechanical technology graduates are expected to drive manufacturing, maintenance, and technological innovation. Employers of labour, however, frequently report dissatisfaction with the practical competence of graduates, resulting in rising unemployment and underemployment (Tani & Kalus, 2023). Over the past thirty years, Nigeria has recorded notable improvements in access to education, resulting in a rising number of graduates from tertiary institutions. These gains are yet to translate into improved employment outcomes for many Nigerian-trained graduates. One of the major obstacles they face is inadequate employability skills. Much of the current curriculum remains outdated, placing greater emphasis on theory while giving limited attention to practical competencies and labour-market needs, which reduces graduates' readiness for today's workplace (Tani & Kalu, 2023; Garis, 2023). National pride is closely linked to the capacity of a nation to produce competent professionals who can compete globally and contribute meaningfully to socioeconomic development (Ha & Jang, 2025). When graduates possess relevant practical skills, they not only secure employment but also enhance productivity, innovation, and the global image of any country (Mabungela & Mtiki, 2024). This study therefore examines the practical skills required by mechanical technology undergraduates for employability and how such skills contribute to national pride.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the growing demand for skilled and employable mechanical technologists due to the technological waves currently across top nations of the world, a significant number of Nigerian graduates remain unemployed or unemployable (Akinbode & Oyelude, 2022). Findings by Kareem (2024) and other scholars like Akinbode & Oyelude (2022) reveal that over 71% of mechanical engineering graduates lack industry-standard hands-on skills, making them unsuitable for immediate employment. Mechanical technology programs are often criticized for excessive emphasis on theory, outdated curricula, inadequate workshop facilities and practical materials, moreso, weak industrial partnerships. Several issues undermining professionalism have been identified in the teaching of mechanical technology, including the training of prospective teachers through poorly regulated satellite or "mushroom" campuses. In addition to these concerns, many TVET departments in Nigerian higher institutions lack adequately equipped laboratories, workshops, and functional infrastructure. Even in institutions where such facilities exist, they are often insufficient, outdated, or in poor condition. Another major challenge is the shortage of experts in curriculum development for Mechanical Technology education (Elom et al., 2021; Kareem, 2024; Tani & Kalu, 2023). This gap limits the ability of programmes to align with internationally accepted TVET standards and practices. Employers consistently further complain about the inability of mechanical technology graduates to operate modern machinery, apply problem-solving skills, and adapt to real workplace environments. This skills mismatch does not only undermine industrial productivity, and increases reliance on foreign expertise, but also weakens national pride. Addressing this problem requires a systematic investigation into the practical skills needed and the gaps within current training systems. Bearing in mind that, perfect practice produce perfect product.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

3. Identify the essential practical skills required for employability of mechanical technology undergraduates.
4. Examine the gaps between current mechanical technology training and industry requirements.
5. Analyze employer expectations regarding technical and soft skills of mechanical technology graduates.

6. Determine how practical skill acquisition enhances employability and national pride in Nigeria.
7. Propose strategies for improving practical skills training in mechanical technology programs.

Research Questions

- iv. What practical skills are essential for mechanical technology undergraduates to be employable in Nigeria?
- v. What gaps exist between current mechanical technology training and industry requirements in Nigeria?
- vi. What technical and soft skills do employers expect from mechanical technology graduates in Nigeria?
- vii. How does improved practical skill acquisition contribute to employability and national pride in Nigeria?
- viii. What strategies can enhance practical skills development among undergraduates in Nigeria?

Significance of the Study

This study is significant to multiple stakeholders like teachers and students, educational institutions, policymakers, employers, and industry partners. Mechanical technology students will become more skillful, and prepared for labor market success. Educational institutions can also use the findings to reform curricula and improve training facilities. Policymakers will also benefit from our real evidence-based recommendations for technical education reforms. Employers and industry partners may leverage the study to strengthen collaboration with institutions. The study will also contribute to national development by linking graduate employability with national pride and industrial growth.

Literature Review

Concept of Employability

Employability according to Santanu (2022) describes the combination of abilities, understanding, and personal qualities that enhance a person's chances of getting a job and performing well in it. It goes beyond simply securing employment to include staying employed, moving between jobs, and adjusting to evolving workplace demands over the course of a career. As a result, employability is essential not only for individual career growth but also for organizational effectiveness, workforce development, and broader economic progress.

According to the Yale School of Management (2024), employability skills combine personal qualities with practical competencies that make individuals appealing to employers. In today's workplace, organizations value people who can balance technical know-how with the ability to operate effectively in complex social and digital settings. These skills form the foundation that allows individuals to function confidently in the workplace, respond to challenges, and add real value within a team.

Santanu (2022) supported this idea because these individuals work alongside technical skills, enabling employees not just to perform their tasks but to succeed in a wide range of work environments. According to Santanu (2022), having strong employability skills equips individuals to handle difficulties, work productively with diverse colleagues, and support the achievement of organizational objectives (Santanu, 2022). The researcher also agrees that employability refers to the combination of skills, knowledge, attitudes, and competencies that enable individuals to secure and sustain employment. This is because employability goes beyond academic achievement to include practical competence and adaptability (Lamri & Lubart, 2023).

Mechanical Technology Practical Skills

Mechanical technology practical skills include machining operations, welding and fabrication, equipment maintenance (Elom et al., 2021), CNC operations, CAD/CAM proficiency, and safety practices. In addition to the technical expertise in mechanical technology, technologists need several essential supporting skills. These include a strong attention to detail to achieve accurate and high-quality results, problem-solving abilities to quickly detect and resolve issues that may affect productivity or quality standards, and the flexibility to adapt to changes in materials, equipment, or job requirements (Ralph, 2025). According to Chan (2025), Machining is a manufacturing method in which material is gradually removed from a workpiece to achieve a specific shape or finish. It relies on tools such as cutting

instruments, abrasive wheels, and discs to eliminate excess material through direct contact with the work piece. This approach is commonly applied to raw stock materials like flat bars and rods, as well as to welded or cast components that require further shaping.

A wide range of products are created through machining, including automotive components, drill bits, plaques, nuts and bolts, flanges, and many other industrial parts and tools. Often referred to as traditional machining, the process is defined by the physical interaction between the cutting tool and the work piece, allowing precise material removal and accurate production of finished components (Chan, 2025). According to Zak (2025) welding and fabrication technology centers on the design, formation, and assembly of metal components and structures. Fabrication covers activities such as cutting, shaping, and fitting metal parts together, while welding involves permanently joining these components through the application of heat or pressure. This area of technology plays a vital role across sectors including construction, manufacturing, aerospace, and automotive industries. It blends hands-on technical expertise with the use of advanced equipment such as CNC cutting machines and robotic welding systems.

Skills Gap in Nigeria

Several scholars have so far taken notice of the wide skills gap in the engineering sector in Nigeria (Elijah et al., 2023; Adoghe, 2023; Emumejaye & Osiga-Aigbangbee, 2021). Evidently, as a result of ongoing changes in the labour market, policymakers, employers, and educators in Nigeria are increasingly confronted with the problem of skills mismatch among recent graduates. This mismatch arises when the competencies employers require do not align with the skills possessed by job seekers, leading to reduced productivity, underemployment, and slower economic growth (Adekanmbi & Ukpere, 2021).

Akintayo et al. (2020) also supported the views of Adekanmbi & Ukpere (2021) while observing an obvious gap between the capabilities of graduates and the skill demands of the Nigerian workforce. Despite the growing number of university and college graduates, many lack the practical and technical skills needed to perform effectively in modern, technology-driven industries. According to Adekanmbi and Ukpere (2021), this skills gap can be attributed to several factors, including rapid technological advancements, shifting market demands, inadequate training facilities and learning opportunities, and limited motivation among graduates to update or acquire new skills.

Employer Expectations

Howard and Kvilhaug (2025) stated regarding employer expectations that in the competitive job market in these recent times, both technical and soft skills play essential roles, and success often depends on finding the right balance between them. Technical skills refer to the specific knowledge and abilities required to perform particular job tasks, while soft skills involve the interpersonal qualities that help individuals communicate, collaborate, and function effectively in the workplace (Howard & Kvilhaug, 2025). Lamri and Lubart (2023) also opined that technical skills, often described as hard skills, are directly related to the core responsibilities of a job. They enable professionals to handle the technical demands of their roles efficiently. For example, software developers must understand programming languages and keep up with new frameworks to remain effective (Lamri & Lubart, 2023).

Langer (2025) focused on the top skills employers are looking for in 2025 and stated that according to the National Association of Colleges & Employers (NACE), employers are increasingly prioritizing specific competencies when assessing job applicants, as highlighted in their Job Outlook 2025 survey.

In the same vein, Addimando (2024) remarked that another major expectation of every employer is that the employee should know how to effectively communicate. Communication remains a foundational skill in nearly every profession, and its importance has grown further in the digital era. Written communication, in particular, has gained prominence, as employees are frequently required to convey ideas through emails, reports, and online content.

Strategies for Skills Development

Atkinson (2024) stated that work-based learning and the integration of real workplace experience into tertiary education are central features of the vocational education and training (VET) system. Also, traditionally speaking, this has been achieved through apprenticeships and traineeships, which place strong emphasis on learning directly in the workplace, as well as through institution-based programs

designed with a clear work focus. More recently, universities have placed growing emphasis on work-integrated learning as part of their academic programs (Atkinson, 2024).

Work-integrated learning is built around the deliberate connection of students' academic studies with practical workplace experience. Its increasing importance is reflected in initiatives such as the *National Work Integrated Learning Strategy* introduced in 2015. This strategy which was developed through collaboration between universities and industry is aimed to expand work-integrated learning opportunities and strengthen relationships with employers. But then, despite this strong commitment to work-based approaches across post-secondary education, both VET providers and universities continue to encounter difficulties in effectively engaging industry partners and employers (Billett, 2022; Cedefop, 2023; Ferguson et al., 2021).

Successful implementation in either context relies on several key factors, including clear communication, continuous interaction between stakeholders, flexible delivery approaches, committed and capable educators who support students, motivated learners, the use of intermediary organizations to coordinate activities, and strong leadership from both business and educational sectors to champion these learning models within communities and organizations (Billett, 2022; Cedefop, 2023).

Main Findings

Fig 1.2: Distribution of Main Challenges affecting Employability

The pie chart illustrates the relative contribution of major challenges affecting employability. Lack of practical skills accounts for the largest share, confirming reports that over 71% of graduates are not industry-ready. Yakubu (2025) opined that from recent data suggest that roughly 55% of young people in Nigeria are either unemployed or underemployed, largely because they lack the practical and technical skills currently required in the labour market. But he suggested that with the rapid rise of technologies such as artificial intelligence, robotics, machine learning, and big data, relying on theoretical knowledge alone is no longer sufficient to remain competitive. In response to this shift, there is a growing need to equip young people with hands-on, relevant skills that allow them to succeed in a fast-changing,

technology-driven economy and stay aligned with emerging trends within the tech ecosystem (Yakubu, 2025).

DISCUSSION

The findings presented in Table 1 above were derived from a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) conducted to identify, analyze, and synthesize existing empirical and conceptual studies on mechanical technology practical skills, graduate employability, and industry expectations, particularly within Nigeria and comparable developing economies. The SLR approach was adopted to ensure methodological rigor, transparency, and replicability in the identification of recurring themes and gaps in the literature. The review followed a structured, multi-stage process adapted from established guidelines in educational and engineering research. At the planning stage, clear review objectives were defined. The review sought to answer the following core questions:

1. What practical skills are required for employability of mechanical technology undergraduates?
2. What deficiencies exist in current training practices?
3. What institutional and industrial factors influence graduate employability?

Search keywords and phrases such as mechanical technology practical skills, engineering graduate employability, skills gap in Nigeria, industry expectations, technical education curriculum, and work-integrated learning were developed to guide the search process. Relevant studies were identified through systematic searches of academic databases and credible online sources, including Google Scholar, ResearchGate, ScienceDirect, institutional repositories, and selected education and engineering journals. In addition, industry and policy reports from reputable sources such as Independent Newspaper Nigeria, and international organizations were consulted to capture current industry perspectives. A total of 68 publications were initially identified during the search process. The screening stage involved removing duplicate records and studies that were not directly relevant to mechanical technology, employability, or practical skills acquisition. Inclusion criteria required that studies:

- Focus on mechanical, engineering, or technical education;
- Address practical skills, employability, or industry readiness;
- Be published between 2015 and 2024 to ensure relevance;
- Be peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, institutional reports, or reputable industry publications.

Studies focusing solely on theoretical education without employability implications were excluded. After screening and eligibility assessment, 32 publications met the inclusion criteria and were retained for detailed analysis. Data were extracted from the selected studies using a thematic analysis approach. The extracted data were coded and grouped into recurring themes. Frequencies of similar observations across studies were noted to determine the relative prominence of each issue. Observations that appeared consistently across multiple studies were considered significant findings. The details of the SLR is in Appendix 1 to 3.

CONCLUSION

This study concludes that practical skills acquisition is central to the employability of mechanical technology undergraduates. The persistent skills gap in Nigeria continues to undermine the industrial growth and our shared national pride. Strengthening practical training through curriculum reform, improved infrastructure, and industry collaboration will produce competent graduates capable of contributing to national development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Mechanical technology curricula should be reviewed to emphasize competency-based practical training.
2. Institutions should upgrade workshop facilities and incorporate modern industrial equipment.
3. Strong partnerships between institutions and industries should be established.

4. Work-integrated learning and extended industrial training should be mandatory.
5. Government and stakeholders should invest in technical education to enhance national pride.

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